

Antimicrobial Resistant Bacteria Transmission between Humans and Companion Animals: A Protocol for a Scoping Review

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Rationale

The use of antimicrobials for treating bacterial diseases in human and veterinary medicine is one of the most important scientific discoveries; however, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has become a critical problem in modern medicine.¹ Antimicrobial resistance occurs when bacteria, parasites, viruses or fungi develop an ability to survive in the presence of antimicrobials.² Veterinarians often prescribe medically important antimicrobials that are commonly used in people to dogs and cats³, and this drug use gives rise to antimicrobial resistant bacteria, which may be transmitted among individuals and species.³

The transmission of antimicrobial resistant bacteria is a bidirectional pathway between humans and pets.³ The bacteria can be transmitted through direct contact between humans and their pets, or indirect exposure to environmental bacteria.⁴ According to a survey of 18 dogs and their owners in 2009, 68.8% of dog owners spend more than 30 hours with their dogs, 50% allowed dogs to sleep in their beds, 50% allowed their dog to lick their faces, and 50% shared food with their dogs.⁵ Two relevant studies showed that behaviors of pet owners such as allowing dogs to lick their faces and handling their dogs' feces have potential influence on resistant bacterial transmission.^{6,7} Therefore, the transmission of antimicrobial resistant bacteria has become a One Health issue in the world.

A scoping review is a type of evidence synthesis approach that includes an analysis of a great range of literature and studies, and it aims to provide a descriptive overview of a broad question.⁵ A scoping review is used to determine the scope of a given topic and map the body of literature as a way of providing a sweeping overview of a topic that may have little or disparate published information.⁸ There is a wide variety of information in published reports on human-pet antimicrobial resistance transmission, so conducting a scoping review is the best method to identify and evaluate available evidence on this topic.

According to a 2019 study, in the US, over 67% of households reported having pets⁹, suggesting that household transmission of antimicrobial resistance between humans and pets could affect millions of Americans. Globally, it is estimated that over half the population has at least one pet, with dogs and cats being the most popular.¹⁰ Therefore, antimicrobial resistance transmission between pets and people should be given more attention. This scoping review will focus on the antimicrobial resistance transmission between people and pets, and will include all primary research studies, systematic reviews, and other scoping reviews that are eligible and related to this topic.

Research Questions and Objectives:

The topic of this project is to identify the existing evidence of antimicrobial resistant bacteria transmission (phenomenon of Interest) between people and pets (dogs and cats) (Population) in the world (Context). The goal of this project is to identify and characterize studies related to the topic through a systematic search of the chosen databases.

The objectives of this project include:

- To extract data from the included studies
- To identify the locations, risk factors, determinants, and characteristics of the antimicrobial resistant bacteria transmission between humans and pets
- To provide information for researchers to identify existing available evidence and knowledge gaps
- To provide a precursor for future studies on this topic

Study Selection

Inclusion criteria

(1) Language: Studies must be published in English or Mandarin.

(2) Types of study: Primary research, narrative reviews, systematic reviews, or scoping reviews. Narrative reviews will only be used to identify relevant primary research; they will not be included in the data charting process. Conference abstracts will not be included in this review if the full text is not found.

(3) Eligible Population of Interest: Domestic cats (*Felis catus*), dogs (*Canis familiaris*), and humans who have contact with cats or dogs, are the eligible population of interest for this scoping review. AMR bacteria must be detected from either samples of both humans and pets or only samples from humans if the transmission of this bacteria from pets is the primary means of infection in humans.

(4) Eligible Phenomenon of Interest: Studies that are related to antimicrobial resistant bacteria transmission between humans and pets (cats and dogs) are eligible for this scoping review. Studies of antimicrobial resistant bacteria transmission between humans and pets (cats and dogs) are eligible for this review; the bacteria must be transmitted from humans to pets or from pets to humans either directly or indirectly (e.g. via a shared environment). The transmission among humans only or pets only is not eligible for this review. Transmission from a separate source to both humans and pets is also not eligible for this review. There are no restrictions on the genus or species of bacteria.

(5) Eligible Countries: All countries in the world are eligible for this scoping review.

Exclusion Criteria

Studies that do not meet all of the inclusion criteria above will not be included in this scoping review.

Information sources

The following databases will be searched to identify the eligible studies using the designed search strategy: Medline (PubMed), CABI Global Health, Scopus, Google Scholar, ProQuest Theses and Dissertations Global. The key word search was developed by the authors of the

review with input from an experienced librarian. Search results will be deduplicated with Mendeley reference management software. Additional studies will be identified from forward and backward reference screening of studies that meet the inclusion criteria following full-text review. Forward searching will be done with Web of Science or Google Scholar cited reference searches.

Review Process

All studies found via the chosen information sources will be added to Covidence and will be reviewed and assessed by a review team of four reviewers, with each study assessed by two reviewers. Any disagreement among reviewers will be resolved by discussion of the entire review team. The number of studies that are excluded from this scoping review will be recorded during each review process. The reason for exclusion at the full text review stage will be recorded.

The review team will test the title and abstract screening process on 100 studies to refine the process for clarity and consistency, as measured by interrater reliability. The full text review and data charting process will be tested on 5 studies.

1. The review team will first review the titles and abstracts of the research found via information sources to answer the following questions:
 - Is this study written in English or Mandarin?
 - Is this study a primary research, narrative review, scoping review, or systematic review?
 - Does this study focus on the targeted population of this review (dogs and/or cats plus humans who have contact with dogs and/or cats)?
 - Does this study focus on antimicrobial resistant bacteria?

Response options to each question are “yes”, “no” and “unclear”. If there is an answer “no” to one of the above questions, this review will be excluded. Studies with an “unclear” answer will be re-assessed at the full-text review stage to answer the above questions.

2. The review team will review the full text of studies with the answer “yes” to all questions of process 1 according to the following questions:
 - Can the full text of the study be acquired?
 - Does this study include cases of AMR transmission between pets (dogs and cats) and humans?
 - Were any AMR bacteria detected from the samples of both the pets and people who have had contact with the pets?
 - If AMR bacteria were only detected from the samples of humans, are pets the primary source of infections with the bacteria in humans?

If there is an answer “no” to one of the above questions, this review will be excluded and the reason for exclusion will be recorded.

Exclusion reasons:

- The study is not a primary research, narrative review, scoping review, or systematic review.

- The study does not focus on any of the targeted population.
- The study does not focus on antimicrobial resistant bacteria.
- The study does not include any case of AMR transmission between pets (dogs and cats) and humans.
- The study does not include details of AMR bacteria detected from samples.
- The full text of the study cannot be acquired.

Data Charting

Data items:

- General information:
 - the locations of cases (country, state if applicable)
 - year of publication
 - language
 - study design
- Targeted population:
 - pet species (dogs or cats)
 - human role relative to pet species (e.g. pet owner, veterinarian, etc.)
- AMR bacteria:
 - isolated bacteria species
 - the use of antibiotics in the pets or humans
 - timing of antibiotic use relative to the infection
 - the types of antimicrobial susceptibility testing used in research
- Means of transmission:
 - direct contact or indirect contact or unknown
 - details of contact type if available
 - the sites of infection

Data Extraction process:

Data from all eligible studies will be charted using a standard form to collect the above data items. This form will be designed and used by the entire review team during data extraction process to identify relevant information and detailed data from eligible studies.

Synthesis of Results

The data extracted from all eligible studies will be analyzed and summarized using figures and tables. All eligible studies will be grouped by different categories (e.g. study design, means of transmission, etc.) if possible and further analyzed.

Appendix A. Search Strategy

Medline (via PubMed):

Search number	Search string

#1	"Drug Resistance, Microbial"[Mesh] OR resistan*[tiab] OR "Genes, MDR"[Mesh] OR "Microbial Sensitivity Tests"[Mesh] OR sensitiv*[tiab] OR susceptib*[tiab]
#2	"Escherichia coli"[Mesh] OR alkalescens-dispar[tiab] OR bacillus[tiab] OR bacterium coli[tiab] OR bacterium E3[tiab] OR coli bacterium[tiab] OR coli bacillus[tiab] OR colon bacillus[tiab] OR enterococcus coli[tiab] OR escherichia coli[tiab] OR e coli[tiab] OR "Enterobacteriaceae"[Mesh] OR Enterobacteriaceae[tiab] OR "Salmonella"[Mesh] OR salmonell*[tiab] OR S Typhimurium[tiab] OR "Campylobacter"[Mesh] OR campylobacter*[tiab] OR Campylobacter jejuni [tiab] OR "Staphylococcus"[Mesh] OR Staphylococc*[tiab] OR MRSA[tiab] OR MRCoNS[tiab] OR "Klebsiella"[Mesh] OR Klebsiella[tiab] OR K pneumoniae[tiab] OR "Vancomycin-Resistant Enterococci"[Mesh] OR Vancomycin-Resistant[tiab] OR enterococci[tiab] OR "Enterococcus"[Mesh] OR enterococcus[tiab] OR enterobacter*[tiab] OR ESBL [tiab] OR "Brucella canis"[Mesh] OR Brucella canis[tiab] OR Brucellosis[tiab] OR "Leptospira"[Mesh] OR Leptospira[tiab] OR Leptospirosis[tiab] OR "Salmonella enterica"[Mesh] OR Salmonella enterica[tiab] OR Salmonellosis[tiab] OR "Bartonella henselae"[Mesh] OR Bartonella henselae [tiab] OR cat scratch disease[tiab] OR cat scratch fever[tiab] OR "Coxiella burnetii"[Mesh] OR Coxiella burnetii[tiab] OR Q fever[tiab] OR coxiellosis[tiab] OR "Yersinia pestis"[Mesh] OR Yersinia pestis[tiab] OR plague[tiab] OR "Capnocytophaga"[Mesh] OR Capnocytophaga[tiab] OR "Yersinia enterocolitica"[Mesh] OR Yersinia enterocolitica[tiab] OR yersiniosis[tiab] OR "Bacteria"[Mesh] OR bacteria[tiab] OR bacterium[tiab] OR bacterial[tiab]
#3	"Disease Transmission, Infectious"[Mesh] OR transmit*[tiab] OR infect*[tiab] OR contamina*[tiab] OR spread*[tiab] OR shar*[tiab] OR disseminat*[tiab]
#4	"Dogs"[Mesh] OR dog[tiab] OR dogs[tiab] OR canine[tiab] OR canis familiaris[tiab] OR "Cats"[Mesh] OR cat[tiab] OR cats[tiab] OR feline[tiab] OR felis catus[tiab] OR "Pets"[Mesh] OR pet[tiab] OR pets[tiab] OR Companion animal*[tiab]
#5	"humans" [Mesh] OR human*[tiab] OR household member*[tiab] OR owner*[tiab] OR people[tiab] or person[tiab]
#6	English[language] OR Chinese[language]
#7	#1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 AND #5 AND #6

Scopus

Search number	Search string
#1	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("resistan*" OR "susceptib*" OR "sensitiv*")
#2	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Escherichia coli" OR "alkalescens-dispar" OR "bacillusa" OR "bacterium coli" OR "bacterium E3" OR "coli bacterium" OR "colibacillus" OR "colon bacillus" OR "enterococcus coli" OR "escherichia coli" OR "e coli" OR "salmonella*" OR "S Typhimurium" OR "campylobacter*" OR "C jejuni" OR

	"Staphylococc*" OR "MRSA" OR "MRCoNS" OR "Klebsiella" OR "K pneumoniae" OR "Vancomycin-Resistant Enterococci" OR "ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae" OR "ESBL-E" OR "Brucella canis" OR "Brucellosis" OR "Leptospira" OR "Leptospirosis" OR "Salmonella enterica" OR "Salmonellosis" OR "Bartonella henselae" OR "cat scratch disease" OR "cat scratch fever" OR "Coxiella burnetii" OR "Q fever" OR "coxiellosis" OR "Yersinia pestis" OR "plague" OR "Capnocytophaga" OR "Yersinia enterocolitica" OR "yersiniosis" OR "bacteria" OR "bacterium" OR "bacterial")
#3	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("transmission" OR "transmit*" OR "infect*" OR "contamina*" OR "infect*" OR "contamina*" OR "spread*" OR "share*" OR "disseminat*")
#4	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("dog" OR "dogs" OR "canine" OR "canis familiaris" OR "cat" OR "cats" OR "feline" OR "felis catus" OR "pet" OR "pets" OR "companion animal*")
#5	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("human" OR "humans" OR "household member*" OR "owner*" OR "people" OR "person")
#6	LANGUAGE ("English" OR "Chinese")
#7	#1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 AND #5 AND #6

Web of Science Core Collection

Search number	Search string
#1	TS=("resistan*" OR "susceptib*" OR "sensitiv*")
#2	TS=("Escherichia coli" OR "alkalescens-dispar" OR "bacillusa" OR "bacterium coli" OR "bacterium E3" OR "coli bacterium" OR "colibacillus" OR "colon bacillus" OR "enterococcus coli" OR "escherichia coli" OR "e coli" OR "salmonella*" OR "S Typhimurium" OR "campylobacter*" OR "C jejuni" OR "Staphylococc*" OR "MRSA" OR "MRCoNS" OR "Klebsiella" OR "K pneumoniae" OR "Vancomycin-Resistant Enterococci" OR "ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae" OR "ESBL-E" OR "Brucella canis" OR "Brucellosis" OR "Leptospira" OR "Leptospirosis" OR "Salmonella enterica" OR "Salmonellosis" OR "Bartonella henselae" OR "cat scratch disease" OR "cat scratch fever" OR "Coxiella burnetii" OR "Q fever" OR "coxiellosis" OR "Yersinia pestis" OR "plague" OR "Capnocytophaga" OR "Yersinia enterocolitica" OR "yersiniosis" OR "bacteria" OR "bacterium" OR "bacterial")
#3	TS= ("transmission" OR "transmit*" OR "infect*" OR "contamina*" OR "spread*" OR "share*" OR "disseminat*")
#4	TS= ("dog" OR "dogs" OR "canine" OR "canis familiaris" OR "cat" OR "cats" OR "feline" OR "felis catus" OR "pet" OR "pets" OR "companion animal*")
#5	TS= ("human" OR "humans" OR "household member*" OR "owner*" OR "people" OR "person")
#6	#1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 AND #5 AND LANGUAGE: (English), Timespan=All years (1900-2020)
#7	#1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 AND #5 AND LANGUAGE: (Chinese), Timespan=All years (1900-2020)

ProQuest Theses and Dissertations Global

Search number	Search string
#1	noft("resistan*" OR "susceptib*" OR "sensitiv*")
#2	noft("Escherichia coli" OR "alkalescens-dispar" OR "bacillusa" OR "bacterium coli" OR "bacterium E3" OR "coli bacterium" OR "colibacillus" OR "colon bacillus" OR "enterococcus coli" OR "escherichia coli" OR "e coli" OR "salmonella*" OR "S Typhimurium" OR "campylobacter*" OR "C jejuni" OR "Staphylococc*" OR "MRSA" OR "MRCoNS" OR "Klebsiella" OR "K pneumoniae" OR "Vancomycin-Resistant Enterococci" OR "ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae" OR "ESBL-E" OR "Brucella canis" OR "Brucellosis" OR "Leptospira" OR "Leptospirosis" OR "Salmonella enterica" OR "Salmonellosis" OR "Bartonella henselae" OR "cat scratch disease" OR "cat scratch fever" OR "Coxiella burnetii" OR "Q fever" OR "coxiellosis" OR "Yersinia pestis" OR "plague" OR "Capnocytophaga" OR "Yersinia enterocolitica" OR "yersiniosis" OR "bacteria" OR "bacterium" OR "bacterial")
#3	noft("transmission" OR "transmit*" OR "infect*" OR "contamina*" OR "spread*" OR "share*" OR "disseminat*")
#4	noft("dog" OR "dogs" OR "canine" OR "canis familiaris" OR "cat" OR "cats" OR "feline" OR "felis catus" OR "pet" OR "pets" OR "companion animal*")
#5	noft("human" OR "humans" OR "household member*" OR "owner*" OR "people" OR "person")
#6	#1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 AND #5, Language: English OR Chinese

CABI: CAB Abstracts and Global Health

Search number	Search string
#1	et:("resistan*" OR "susceptib*" OR "sensitiv*") OR ab: ("resistan*" OR "susceptib*" OR "sensitiv*")
#2	et: ("Escherichia coli" OR "alkalescens-dispar" OR "bacillusa" OR "bacterium coli" OR "bacterium E3" OR "coli bacterium" OR "colibacillus" OR "colon bacillus" OR "enterococcus coli" OR "escherichia coli" OR "e coli" OR "salmonella*" OR "S Typhimurium" OR "campylobacter*" OR "C jejuni" OR "Staphylococc*" OR "MRSA" OR "MRCoNS" OR "Klebsiella" OR "K pneumoniae" OR "Vancomycin-Resistant Enterococci" OR "ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae" OR "ESBL-E" OR "Brucella canis" OR "Brucellosis" OR "Leptospira" OR "Leptospirosis" OR "Salmonella enterica" OR "Salmonellosis" OR "Bartonella henselae" OR "cat scratch disease" OR "cat scratch fever" OR "Coxiella burnetii" OR "Q fever" OR "coxiellosis" OR "Yersinia pestis" OR "plague" OR "Capnocytophaga" OR "Yersinia enterocolitica" OR "yersiniosis" OR "bacteria" OR "bacterium" OR "bacterial") OR

	ab:("Escherichia coli" OR "alkalescens-dispar" OR "bacillusa" OR "bacterium coli" OR "bacterium E3" OR "coli bacterium" OR "colibacillus" OR "colon bacillus" OR "enterococcus coli" OR "escherichia coli" OR "e coli" OR "salmonella*" OR "S Typhimurium" OR "campylobacter*" OR "C jejuni" OR "Staphylococc*" OR "MRSA" OR "MRCoNS" OR "Klebsiella" OR "K pneumoniae" OR "Vancomycin-Resistant Enterococci" OR "ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae" OR "ESBL-E" OR "Brucella canis" OR "Brucellosis" OR "Leptospira" OR "Leptospirosis" OR "Salmonella enterica" OR "Salmonellosis" OR "Bartonella henselae" OR "cat scratch disease" OR "cat scratch fever" OR "Coxiella burnetii" OR "Q fever" OR "coxiellosis" OR "Yersinia pestis" OR "plague" OR "Capnocytophaga" OR "Yersinia enterocolitica" OR "yersiniosis" OR "bacteria" OR "bacterium" OR "bacterial")
#3	et: ("transmission" OR "transmit*" OR "infect*" OR "contamina*" OR "spread*" OR "share*" OR "disseminat*") OR ab: ("transmission" OR "transmit*" OR "infect*" OR "contamina*" OR "spread*" OR "share*" OR "disseminat*")
#4	et: ("dog" OR "dogs" OR "canine" OR "canis familiaris" OR "cat" OR "cats" OR "feline" OR "felis catus" OR "pet" OR "Pets" OR "Companion animal*") OR ab: ("dog" OR "dogs" OR "canine" OR "canis familiaris" OR "cat" OR "cats" OR "feline" OR "felis catus" OR "pet" OR "pets" OR "Companion animal*")
#5	et: ("human" OR "humans" OR "household member*" OR "owner*" OR "people" OR "person") OR ab: ("human" OR "humans" OR "household member*" OR "owner*" OR "people" OR "person")
#6	#1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 AND #5, Refined by: Language: English OR Chinese, year: 1915-2020

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